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CONTENTS

FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN THE EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION OF FREE ECONOMIC ZONES.....	51
Mamadiev Elyor	
IMPROVING ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR THE ESTABLISHMENT AND DEVELOPMENT OF FAMILY GUEST HOUSES	55
Boynazarov Ulugbek Egamberdievich	
IMPROVING METHODS OF ORGANIZING AND DEVELOPING DOMESTIC TOURISM MARKETS IN UZBEKISTAN	61
Daminov Mirvokhid Isroilovich	
THE IMPACT AND SIGNIFICANCE OF INFRASTRUCTURE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE TOURISM SECTOR.....	67
Dilsora Ibodovna Ibodova	
IMPACT OF STUDENTS AGED OVER 40 ON ECONOMIC ACTIVITY AND BUDGETING BASED ON THE COMPETENCY ECOSYSTEM	74
Nigora Ikrom qizi Primova	
ОЦЕНКА ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ПРОМЫШЛЕННЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ ХОРЕЗМСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ: ЭКОНОМЕТРИЧЕСКОЕ МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЕ И СЦЕНАРНОЕ ПРОГНОЗИРОВАНИЕ НА 2026–2030 ГОДЫ	80
Юсуфов Шерзодбек Бахтиёр угли	
IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY FOR ASSESSING THE PROCUREMENT MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN COMMERCIAL ENTERPRISES	87
Ergashev Jahongir Bakhodirovich	
MULTIVARIATE ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF FACTORS AFFECTING HOUSEHOLD INCOME IN SURXONDARYO REGION	93
Abdunazarova Shahnoza Norquchqor qizi	
СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫХ ЦИФРОВЫХ УСЛУГ АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНА И УЗБЕКИСТАНА	99
Юсифов Магамед Исмаил оглу, Гасанли Расул Шахин оглу, Белалова Гузаль Анваровна	
SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE MINING INDUSTRY IN THE CONTEXT OF THE GREEN ECONOMY.....	105
Xudayberdiyeva Kamila Sadiilloyevna, Fozilova Zumrad Ahmadovna	
IMPROVING THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF CLOTHING MANUFACTURING ENTERPRISES IN UZBEKISTAN THROUGH DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION	111
Axmedova Gaziza Azim kizi	
КОМПЛЕКСНАЯ ОЦЕНКА ПОТЕНЦИАЛА РЕГИОНАЛЬНОГО АГРОПРОМЫШЛЕННОГО ИНТЕГРИРОВАНИЯ НА ОСНОВЕ МОДЕЛИ АНР-TOPSIS	115
Аликулов А.Б.	
APPLICATION OF CLUSTER METHODS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM INFRASTRUCTURE AND IMPROVEMENT OF ECONOMIC MECHANISMS IN SAMARKAND CITY	121
Tashov Mizrob Maxmudovich	
THE ROLE AND PROSPECTS OF THE GREEN ECONOMY IN THE SERVICE SECTOR.....	130
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Usmonova Dilfuza Ilkhomovna	
FACTORS AFFECTING THE EFFICIENCY OF REGIONAL ENTERPRISES	135
Nigora Zokirjon qizi Toxirova	
CURRENT STATE OF ATTRACTING INVESTMENTS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM IN THE REGIONS OF UZBEKISTAN AND THE METHODOLOGY OF ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY INDICATORS	142
Temurbek Olimovich Mamayunusov	
PRESUPPOSITION SHIFTS IN CROSS-LINGUISTIC RENDERING OF ANECDOTAL NARRATIVES:	

A COMPARATIVE INQUIRY INTO TRIGGER RETENTION AND TRANSFORMATION	148
Umaraliyeva Dildora Taxirjanovna	
DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES AND RURAL PUBLIC SERVICE QUALITY: AN EMPIRICAL ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS	156
Bek Hunsia, Feruza Mansurovna Ollokulova	
COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF WOMEN'S LABOR ACTIVITY ON THE EFFICIENCY OF THE ECONOMIC SYSTEM	164
Ahrorova Asila Abduaziz qizi	
IMPROVING TAX ADMINISTRATION IN THE ENTREPRENEURIAL ENVIRONMENT	170
Azizbek Khurramov	
FORMATION OF FINANCIAL RESULTS AT MOTOR TRANSPORT ENTERPRISES	180
Shanazarova Nilufar Baratovna	
ARIMA-BASED ANALYSIS OF SMALL BUSINESS ACTIVITY IN THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR OF SURKHANDARYA REGION	185
Fayziyeva Aziza Azamat qizi	
ASSESSMENT OF AGRARIAN SECTOR EFFICIENCY THROUGH THE SFA MODEL	192
Utanov Bunyod Kuvandikovich	
АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫМ ВНЕШНИМ ДОЛГОМ	196
Шомуродов Равшан Турсункулович, Жуманазаров Шахобиддин Дилмурод угли	
MODERN METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO MANAGING EDUCATIONAL SERVICES MARKETING IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS	201
Shamshieva Nargizakhon Nosirkhuja kizi	
FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT OF FOREIGN AND DOMESTIC COTTON GINNING ENTERPRISES: COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS, DIAGNOSTICS, AND IMPROVEMENT DIRECTIONS	208
Orif Jumayevich Murodov	
ANALYSIS OF THE INSTITUTIONAL FOUNDATIONS OF STATE INTERVENTION IN THE PRODUCT QUALITY MANAGEMENT PROCESS IN UZBEKISTAN	219
Atakulov Askad Raimkulovich	
ИНТЕГРИРОВАННАЯ МОДЕЛЬ ФОРМАЛИЗАЦИИ НЕФОРМАЛЬНОЙ ЗАНЯТОСТИ И РАСШИРЕНИЯ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ ЗАЩИТЫ В АГРАРНЫХ РЕГИОНАХ (НА ПРИМЕРЕ КАШКАДАРЬИНСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ)	224
Бобоназарова Юлдуз Ботировна	
THE ECONOMIC ESSENCE OF RESOURCE USE EFFICIENCY AND ITS ROLE IN INDUSTRIAL ECONOMICS	229
Baymanova Mavlyuda Djurayevna, Aipova Iroda Ikramovna	
THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT: EVIDENCE FROM DEVELOPING COUNTRIES	234
Ismatova Diyora Sirojiddin qizi, Ubaydullayeva Gulchexra Erkabayevna	
ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ УСТОЙЧИВОСТЬ И РЕСУРСНАЯ АДАПТИВНОСТЬ ОТРАСЛИ МАШИНОСТРОЕНИЯ В РОССИИ, КИТАЕ, ИНДИИ	239
Викторова Наталья Геннадьевна, Абрамчикова Наталья Викторовна, Ван Байянь	
ENSURING ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR HOUSING STOCK MANAGEMENT	249
Aminova Naima Umar qizi	
STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT FOR ECONOMIC GROWTH: PRACTICAL APPROACHES AND IMPROVEMENTS	253
Baymuradov Shokhruxh Makhmudovich, Dilmurodov Komiljon Ahmad o'g'li	
IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF SMALL ENTERPRISES IN THE SERVICE SECTOR (A CASE STUDY OF TASHKENT REGION)	259

Ashirov Alisher	
IMPROVING THE ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR THE TRANSFORMATION OF SERVICE ENTERPRISES IN UZBEKISTAN	264
Kurbanova Rahima Jamshedovna	
INNOVATIVE IDEAS OF YOUNG ENTREPRENEURS AND INFRASTRUCTURE FACTORS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL INNOVATIVE BUSINESSES	270
Ergashev Oybek Khaydaralievich	
MARKETING CHARACTERISTICS OF POSITIONING ORGANIC DRIED FRUIT PRODUCTS IN INTERNATIONAL MARKETS	274
Khidirov Shokhrukh	
TYOLOGIZATION OF THE ECONOMIC POTENTIAL AND DEVELOPMENT CHARACTERISTICS OF THE DISTRICTS OF SURKHANDARYA REGION BASED ON STATISTICAL AND NEURAL NETWORK APPROACHES.....	280
Normurodov Asliddin Alijon ugli	
THE ROLE OF FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN ANALYSING THE THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE AUDIT OF FINANCIAL LIABILITIES	291
Palvanov Xusniddin Bekimmatovich	
DIGITAL SKILLS AND LABOUR PRODUCTIVITY: A SCENARIO ANALYSIS BASED ON AN INTEGRATED STATISTICAL MODEL	297
Madraimov Xabibulla Madaminovich	
АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ СТРУКТУРЫ АКТИВОВ И ПАССИВОВ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫХ БАНКОВ УЗБЕКИСТАНА	303
Т.И. Бобакулов	
АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ ФИНАНСИРОВАНИЯ ВНЕШНЕТОРГОВУЮ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬ КОМПАНИЙ С ДОКУМЕНТАРНЫМИ АККРЕДИТИВАМИ.....	308
М.Т. Ибодуллаева	
ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ИНТЕГРИРОВАННОГО МЕХАНИЗМА УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ОСНОВНЫМИ СРЕДСТВАМИ В УСЛОВИЯХ ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ	312
Мусаева Жамила Кароматовна	
ПРОБЛЕМНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТИ КОММЕРЧЕСКИХ БАНКОВ УЗБЕКИСТАНА	320
Ш.Т. Ибодуллаев	
THE IMPORTANCE OF STATE SUPPORT AND INVESTMENT POLICY IN ENSURING THE FINANCIAL STABILITY OF MASS MEDIA ENTERPRISES.....	325
Sharipova Shahlo Istamovna	
CURRENT STATUS AND DEVELOPMENT TRENDS OF MOTOR TRANSPORT SERVICES	329
Rakhimov Azamat Hamrakulovich	
ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ЭКСТРЕМАЛЬНЫХ МОДЕЛЕЙ В ОЦЕНКЕ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО ПОТЕНЦИАЛА ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯ.....	333
Мусаева Шоира Азимовна	
MULTI-FACTOR ECONOMETRIC MODELS OF WATER RESOURCE USE IN ENSURING REGIONAL ECONOMIC STABILITY.....	341
Xaitbaev Jasurbek Otaxanovich	
СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ ПРАКТИКИ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ИНСТРУМЕНТОВ ЭЛЕКТРОННОГО ДОКУМЕНТООБОРОТА В КОММЕРЧЕСКИХ БАНКАХ.....	345
Шомуродов Равшан Турсункулович	
THE WAYS OF IMPROVING COMPETITIVENESS IN COMPANIES OF THE CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY	350
Buriev Khakim Toshimovich, Usmanov Ilxom Achilovich, Tolibov Abduazim Zoxid ugli	
MACROECONOMIC MODELS AND PROSPECTS OF TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN	357
Sharipboyev Hasanboy Marks ugli, Sharipov Kuvondik Baxtiyorovich	
THE IMPACT OF HRM PRACTICES ON ACADEMIC STAFF WORK EFFICIENCY IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS.....	366
Sultonboyeva Munira Bahodirovna, Sultanova Kamila Muktorali Kizi	

THE ECONOMIC ROLE OF RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE GREEN ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN	374
Inatullayeva Intizor Jamshid qizi	
ОЦЕНКА ФИЗИОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ПОКАЗАТЕЛЕЙ КРУПНОГО РОГАТОГО СКОТА, ЗАВЕЗЁННОГО В РЕСПУБЛИКУ КАРАКАЛПАКСТАН ИЗ-ЗА РУБЕЖА, С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ ЦИФРОВЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ	378
Аскарова Нилуфар Бахтияровна	
COOPERATIVE MECHANISMS FOR REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT: A FRAMEWORK ANALYSIS OF CULTURAL TOURISM ENTERPRISE PARTNERSHIPS.....	382
Shohruzbek Ruziyev	
IMPROVING THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF RESOURCE UTILIZATION IN METALLURGICAL ENTERPRISES: INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE AND MODERN DEVELOPMENT TRENDS	393
Matkuliev Akbar Karimovich	
TAX INCENTIVES GRANTED TO ENTERPRISES LOCATED IN SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONES	397
Torayeva Nafisa Odiljonovna	
REQUIREMENTS FOR TRANSITIONING TO ELECTRONIC BUSINESS AND CONDITIONS FOR DIGITALIZATION.....	402
Ismoilov Diyorbek Ismoiljon ugli	
DEVELOPMENT OF ALTERNATIVE ENERGY AS AN IMPORTANT FACTOR IN ENSURING A SUSTAINABLE ECONOMY AND ENERGY SECURITY	407
Ergash Bobobekov	
ANALYSIS OF WAGE DYNAMICS IN THE EXAMPLE OF SURKHANDARYA REGION BASED ON PANEL DATA.....	412
Abdunazarova Shahnoza Norquchqor kizi	
THE ROLE OF MARKETING STRATEGIES IN IMPROVING THE MARKET COMPETITIVENESS OF CARPET INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES	420
Arzieva Sevinch Shomurot kizi	
CONSUMER PROPERTIES OF FOOD PRODUCTS IN UZBEKISTAN: TRADITIONS, TRANSFORMATION AND NEW QUALITY STANDARDS.....	425
Gayrat Pardaev	
DIRECTIONS FOR STIMULATING ECONOMIC GROWTH THROUGH THE IMPROVEMENT OF THE TAX SYSTEM.....	431
Yakhshimuratova Khasiyat Khudaybergenovna	
THE ROLE OF E-COMMERCE IN THE ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN AND ITS DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS	435
Kambaraliyeva Intizor Suxrobovna	
Aliyarov Olim Abdug‘aparovich	
ISSUES OF IMPROVING PRE-TRIAL TAX DISPUTE RESOLUTION MECHANISMS BASED ON INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE	439
Solihova Xumora Xasan kizi	
INCREASING THE ATTRACTIVENESS OF DIVIDEND POLICY IN UZBEKISTAN COMPANIES.....	446
Akmal Komiljonovich Shermukhamedov	
COMMUNITY-BASED HERITAGE TOURISM MODELS AS A TOOL FOR ENHANCING HANDICRAFT DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN.....	451
Olimjonova Farog‘at Dilmurod qizi	
Amiriddinova Muslima Zayniddin qizi	
ИНСТИТУЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ МЕХАНИЗМЫ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ ЗАЩИТЫ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ В УСЛОВИЯХ ПЕРЕХОДНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ: ОПЫТ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН	458
Шоахмедов Шоҳрух Шорахимович	

OF EFFECTIVE USE OF AGRICULTURAL LAND	464
Umarov Muzaffar Yusupbayevich	
ECONOMIC CONTENT OF INTANGIBLE ASSETS IN THE FIELD OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES AND SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THEIR RECOGNITION	469
Ishankulov Izzatilla Nurillaevich	
DETERMINANTS OF NON-PERFORMING LOANS IN SERVICE SECTOR LENDING AND CREDIT RISK MITIGATION MECHANISMS	473
Nurmukhammedov Abdijabbar Yunusovich	
ESG INTEGRATION PRACTICES INTO CORPORATE CULTURE SYSTEM IN THE JOINTSTOCK SECTOR OF UZBEKISTAN: A CASE STUDY OF “DORI-DARMON” JSC.....	479
Sadikova Muslima Alisher kizi	
DEVELOPMENT OF THE METAL MARKET IN THE TASHKENT REGION AND WAYS TO IMPROVE IT	485
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna	
SMALL BUSINESS AS A CATALYST FOR REGIONAL ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS WITH EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	491
Jo‘rayev Ilhomjon Kamolidinovich	
ISSUES OF DEVELOPING DEPOSIT OPERATIONS IN COMMERCIAL BANKS	497
Rahimov Akmal Matyaqubovich	
IMPROVING TEXTILE LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT IN UZBEKISTAN	503
Isroilov Madaminjon Mukhsinovich	
FEATURES OF SUMMARIZING AND EVALUATING THE RESULTS OF FINANCIAL STATEMENT AUDITING IN UZBEKISTAN PRACTICE	509
Isroil Ismoilovich Meliev	
ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОЕ УПРАВЛЕНИЕ ФИНАНСАМИ И СОЦИАЛЬНОЕ РАВЕНСТВО В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ: ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ МЕТОДОЛОГИИ РЕФА С ДИСТРИБУТИВНЫМ АНАЛИЗОМ НА ОСНОВЕ ПОДХОДА SEQ.....	516
Зокиржонов Мухаммадсодик Равшанбек угли	
FACTORS AFFECTING DAIRY PRODUCTION EFFICIENCY: CORRELATION AND REGRESSION ANALYSIS.....	530
Ergashev M.Y.	
Tairova Z.M.	
METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF COST ACCOUNTING AND ANALYSIS IN AQUACULTURE CLUSTERS: IFRS INTEGRATION, ECONOMETRIC MODELING, AND ESG PERSPECTIVES.....	537
Shodiev Aslam Rahmatilloevich	
APPLICATION OF ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORKS FOR PREDICTING CUSTOMER LOYALTY IN COMMERCIAL BANKS	544
Jumaniyozova Mukaddas	
SUSTAINABLE REGIONAL SPECIALIZATION UNDER WATER SCARCITY: GLOBAL EXPERIENCE AND PROSPECTS FOR UZBEKISTAN	550
Sodiqova Nigora Turayevna	
CURRENT STATE AND STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF EXPORT ACTIVITIES OF BUSINESS ENTITIES IN THE BUKHARA REGION	555
Djurayeva Munira Sadillovna	
EVALUATION OF THE EFFICIENCY OF STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT OF EDUCATIONAL SERVICES EXPORTS IN THE BUKHARA REGION	560
Alimova Shamsiya Abidovna	

ADVANCING AN INTEGRATED STATISTICAL ASSESSMENT METHODOLOGY FOR COMMERCIAL BANKS' DIGITAL ACTIVITIES AND CREDIT PORTFOLIO QUALITY	565
Rakhmatiev Muzaffar Eshdavlatovich	
EFFECTIVENESS OF USING BIOLOGICAL METHODS IN PLANT PROTECTION: STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF DISTRIBUTION STRATEGY AND PRACTICAL IMPLEMENTATION DENSITY	570
Suyundikova Dilafuz Mamarajabovna	

EFFECTIVENESS OF USING BIOLOGICAL METHODS IN PLANT PROTECTION: STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF DISTRIBUTION STRATEGY AND PRACTICAL IMPLEMENTATION DENSITY

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Annotation. This article presents a statistical analysis of the effectiveness of using biological agents in plant protection, with particular attention to discrepancies between the planned quantities and actual distribution of these agents across agricultural fields. The study examines the application of entomophagous biological products, such as Oltinko'z, Trichogramma, and Bracon, in wheat and cotton fields during the 2024 harvest season in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Differences between planned and actual implementation levels are identified based on such indicators as the number of biolaboratories, the number of farms, the quantity of biological products, and their distribution density across fields. The article also examines the ecological and economic benefits of biological protection measures and proposes statistical approaches for assessing their impact on crop productivity.

Keywords: biological protection, entomophages, bioproducts, Oltinko'z, Trichogramma, Bracon, plant protection, statistical analysis, planned and actual discrepancy, distribution density, ecological safety, biolaboratory, farming enterprise.

Аннотация. В данной статье представлен статистический анализ эффективности применения биологических средств защиты растений с особым акцентом на выявление расхождений между запланированными и фактическими объемами их распределения на сельскохозяйственных угодьях. Исследование посвящено применению энтомофагов — златоглазки (Oltinko'z), трихограммы (Trichogramma) и бракона (Bracon) — на посевах пшеницы и хлопчатника в период урожайного сезона 2024 года в Республике Узбекистан. Различия между плановыми и фактическими показателями внедрения определены на основе таких статистических индикаторов, как количество биолaborаторий, число фермерских хозяйств, объем биологической продукции и плотность её распределения на сельскохозяйственных площадях. Кроме того, в статье рассматриваются экологические и экономические преимущества биологических методов защиты растений, а также предлагаются статистические подходы к оценке их влияния на урожайность сельскохозяйственных культур.

Ключевые слова: биологическая защита растений, энтомофаги, биопрепараты, златоглазка (Oltinko'z), трихограмма, бракон, защита растений, статистический анализ, расхождение между плановыми и фактическими показателями, плотность распределения, экологическая безопасность, биолaborатория, фермерское хозяйство.

INTRODUCTION

Plant protection against harmful organisms plays a crucial role in ensuring sustainable agricultural development, increasing crop productivity, and protecting agro-ecosystems. Since the intensive use of traditional chemical agents may lead to both economic and ecological challenges, the importance of biological control methods has increased significantly. In this context, the use of biological agents, particularly natural entomophages such as Oltinko'z, Trichogramma, and Bracon, has become one of the key priorities of national agricultural policy, as these methods offer environmentally safe solutions for pest control.

Resolution No. PQ-4861 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated October 13, 2020, defines specific measures to further improve the activities of the State Plant Quarantine Service. The resolution sets

clear tasks for the scientific modernization of the plant protection system, expanding the production of biological agents, and organizing their practical application in agricultural fields. It also emphasizes the need to improve the activities of biological laboratories, promote the effective use of entomophages against local pests, and strengthen mechanisms for state support of biological protection measures.

Nevertheless, statistical analyses of discrepancies between the planned and actual quantities of biological products distributed across agricultural fields, the reasons for these discrepancies, regional distribution density indicators, and the effectiveness of biological protection measures have not yet been sufficiently systematized. This makes the study of this topic scientifically and practically relevant.

This study examines the effectiveness of using biological agents in plant protection, the discrepancies between planned and actual implementation levels in their regional distribution, distribution density, and related statistical indicators. The analysis focuses on data for 2024, including the number of farms, the volume of biological products distributed to wheat and cotton fields, planned and actual area coverage in hectares, the quantity of products in millions of units, and percentage differences.

The results of the study are of practical importance for forming a sustainable and environmentally friendly plant protection system in Uzbekistan's agriculture, ensuring the efficient use of resources, evaluating and improving the activities of biological laboratories, and making scientifically grounded agronomic decisions.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In recent years, the use of biological agents that are both ecologically safe and economically efficient has become increasingly important in plant protection as an alternative to chemical agents. Biological control methods involving entomophages, such as *Oltinko'z*, *Trichogramma*, *Bracon*, and other beneficial organisms, are considered an important factor in maintaining the stability of agro-ecosystems and ensuring effective pest control.

Resolution No. PQ-4861 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated October 13, 2020, defines measures aimed at improving the activities of the State Plant Quarantine Service, developing the network of biological laboratories, introducing modern technologies, and expanding the production and application of entomophages. Based on this document, a planned and systematic approach to the use of biological plant protection agents has been established in the country [1].

The scientific literature examines various aspects of the use of entomophages. In particular, Karimov B. K. studied their agro-biological foundations [2], Rustamova D. analyzed their impact on ecosystems [3], and Islomov A. examined their economic efficiency [4]. In addition, Yoqubov S. investigated the advantages and limitations of distribution mechanisms across regions [5]. International organizations, including FAO [6] and ICARDA [7], have also emphasized the role of biological control methods in ensuring sustainable agriculture.

The effective operation of biological laboratories largely depends on their material and technical base, the availability of qualified personnel, and their regional location. According to the research of A. Tursunov [8], these factors directly influence the production of biological products and their timely delivery to agricultural fields.

In local practice, insufficient attention has been paid to comparing the planned and actual distribution density of biological products and conducting statistical analysis of the factors influencing their effectiveness. This further emphasizes the scientific relevance and practical significance of the present research topic.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study examines the effectiveness of using biological agents in plant protection within the agricultural sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the basis of statistical methods. The main focus is placed on analyzing the planned distribution of biological agents, such as *Oltinko'z*, across agricultural fields in different regions and comparing these plans with their actual implementation in practice. Based on this approach, the performance of biological laboratories in the country and the level of their practical utilization were evaluated using specific statistical indicators.

In the course of the study, official statistical reports for 2024 provided by the Ministry of Agriculture and other relevant organizations were used as the main data source. Based on these reports, graphical analysis, percentage difference analysis, time series analysis, and comparative analysis by regional distribution were conducted.

The discrepancies between planned and actual indicators were recorded in terms of both percentage and quantitative differences, and separate statistical results were presented for each biological agent. In particular, an efficiency analysis was carried out based on the distribution density of biological products per hectare, measured in millions of units or kilograms, as well as their coverage rate across regions.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In recent years, the modernization of the plant protection system in Uzbekistan's agriculture has accelerated significantly. In particular, in 2024, the widespread use of biological agents was observed in pest control and preventive protection measures. Biological products produced by biolaboratories in the country, including entomophages such as Oltinko'z, have strengthened the mechanism for protecting agricultural crops while reducing reliance on chemical agents.

This section provides a statistical analysis of the planned and actual distribution of biological products to wheat and cotton fields across regions and districts in 2024. The analysis covers distribution density, discrepancies between planned and actual implementation, and efficiency levels across different regions. The study is based on official statistical data obtained from the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan and biological laboratories.

Through this analysis, the practical status of biological control methods across regions is identified, including the level of resource utilization, positive outcomes, and areas requiring further improvement. In addition, the study forms a scientific basis for making decisions based on sustainable, environmentally friendly, and economically viable approaches to plant protection (Table 1).

Table 1
Indicators of the Distribution of Oltinko'z Biological Products to
Agricultural Fields by Biolaboratories for Pest Control and Preventive Measures¹

No.	Region	Number of Biolaboratories	Wheat Field Area, ha	Area Treated with Oltinko'z Biological Product, ha	Quantity of Oltinko'z Biological Product, million units
1	Republic of Karakalpakstan	69	63,000	62,930	62.9
2	Andijan	86	82,000	79,568	79.6
3	Bukhara	35	76,894	77,141	77.1
4	Jizzakh	40	105,000	72,269	72.3
5	Kashkadarya	70	140,000	139,107	139.1
6	Navoi	11	38,039	31,386	31.4
7	Namangan	25	68,000	102,479	102.5
8	Samarkand	32	77,123	77,133	77.1
9	Surkhandarya	65	89,324	114,535	114.5
10	Syrdarya	35	78,000	75,109	75.1
11	Tashkent	43	103,000	70,311	70.3
12	Fergana	43	94,770	92,451	92.5
13	Khorezm	85	33,200	66,400	66.4

The data presented in the table make it possible to conduct a comparative analysis of the planned and actual volumes of Oltinko'z biological products distributed to wheat fields across different regions. These indicators serve as an important statistical basis for evaluating the effectiveness of using biological agents in plant protection.

Within the framework of this research, it is proposed to apply several statistical methods to conduct an in-depth and systematic analysis of the data. These methods include the following:

1. Assessment of the effectiveness of distributing Oltinko'z biological products to crop fields by biolaboratories for pest control and preventive purposes through percentage analysis of the gap between planned and actual implementation. This method involves calculating actual performance as a percentage of the planned volume for each region. It makes it possible to evaluate the efficiency of biological product distribution and determine the extent to which the planned outcomes have been achieved (Table 2).

$$\text{Plan Fulfillment (\%)} = \frac{\text{Actual Volume Implemented (ha)}}{\text{Planned Volume (ha)}} * 100\%$$

¹ author's development

Table 2. Effectiveness of Distributing Oltinko'z Biological Products to Crop Fields by Biolaboratories for Pest Control and Preventive Measures²

No.	Region	Wheat Area, ha	Actually Covered Area, ha	Plan Fulfillment, %
1	Republic of Karakalpakstan	63,000	62,930	99.89
2	Andijan	82,000	79,568	97.00
3	Bukhara	76,894	77,141	100.30
4	Jizzakh	105,000	72,269	68.83
5	Kashkadarya	140,000	139,107	99.36
6	Navoi	38,039	31,386	82.52
7	Namangan	68,000	102,479	150.70
8	Samarkand	77,123	77,133	100.01
9	Surkhandarya	89,324	114,535	128.22
10	Syrdarya	78,000	75,109	96.29
11	Tashkent	103,000	70,311	68.26
12	Fergana	94,770	92,451	97.55
13	Khorezm	33,200	66,400	200.00

In 2024, the analysis of the application of the Oltinko'z biological agent to wheat fields across the Republic of Uzbekistan as part of pest control and preventive measures showed that, in many regions, the actual use of this product exceeded the planned targets. Overall, the application of the agent was planned for 1,048,350 hectares of wheat fields; however, in practice, it was applied to 1,060,819 hectares. As a result, the plan fulfillment rate reached 101.19%.

1. Regional Analysis of Plan Fulfillment. The regional analysis shows considerable variation in the implementation of the planned distribution of the Oltinko'z biological product. The highest level of plan fulfillment was recorded in Khorezm Region, where implementation reached 200.00%, indicating the most intensive application of biological control measures. Similarly, implementation exceeded the planned targets in Namangan Region (150.70%) and Surkhandarya Region (128.22%), suggesting either a greater need for biological protection due to higher pest pressure or a conservative estimation of the initial distribution plan (Figure 1).

In contrast, Jizzakh Region (68.83%) and Tashkent Region (68.26%) recorded the lowest plan fulfillment rates. These deviations may reflect differences in local implementation conditions, resource allocation, logistical capacity, or updated field requirements during the implementation period (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Rate of Plan Fulfillment for the Distribution of Oltinko'z by Region³

² author's development

³ author's development

In the remaining regions, plan fulfillment ranged from approximately 82% to 100%, indicating a relatively close correspondence between planned and actual implementation. This suggests that the activities of regional biolaboratories were generally well coordinated and effectively managed.

Overall, although the nationwide distribution of the Oltinko'z biological product slightly exceeded the planned target, the substantial regional differences highlight the importance of improving regional planning mechanisms, strengthening monitoring systems, and enhancing the allocation of biological resources to ensure a more balanced and efficient implementation of biological plant protection measures.

2. Assessment of the Distribution Density of Biological Products. The next stage of the analysis examines the distribution density of biological products by determining the number of millions of biological units applied per hectare in each region. In modern plant protection systems, evaluating the effectiveness of biological control requires not only measuring the total quantity of biological products distributed but also assessing the intensity of their application across cultivated areas.

In particular, the distribution density of the Oltinko'z biological product on wheat fields—expressed as the number of millions of biological units applied per hectare—serves as an important indicator of resource utilization efficiency and the quality of biological protection measures.

This density indicator provides more than a comparative measure of the planned and actual quantities of biological products distributed across regions. It also enables a detailed assessment of the efficiency of biological control practices, the balance of regional resource allocation, and the operational performance of biolaboratories. Furthermore, it provides a statistical basis for identifying regional disparities and improving future planning and management of biological plant protection programs (Table 3).

$$\text{Biological Product Density} = \frac{\text{Quantity (mln units)}}{\text{Hectares of Wheat}}$$

Table 3
Wheat Area and Biological Product Density by Regions of Uzbekistan⁴

No	Region Name	G'alla maydoni (ga)	Miqdor (mln.dona)	Zichlik (mln.dona/ga)
1	Qoraqalpog'iston Respublikasi	63,000	62.9	0.998
2	Republic of Karakalpakstan	82,000	79.6	0.971
3	Andijan	76,894	77.1	1.003
4	Bukhara	105,000	72.3	0.688
5	Jizzakh	140,000	139.1	0.993
6	Kashkadarya	38,039	31.4	0.826
7	Navoi	68,000	102.5	1.507
8	Namangan	77,123	77.1	1.000
9	Samarkand	89,324	114.5	1.282
10	Surkhandarya	78,000	75.1	0.963
11	Syrdarya	103,000	70.3	0.682
12	Tashkent	94,770	92.5	0.976
13	Fergana	33,200	66.4	2.000

This table presents data on wheat cultivation areas, distribution volume, and wheat treatment density, expressed in million units per hectare, across various regions of Uzbekistan. The following key aspects should be taken into account when conducting a general analysis of the table.

First, there is significant variation in wheat cultivation areas across the regions of Uzbekistan. The largest wheat-growing areas are observed in Kashkadarya Region, with 140,000 hectares, Jizzakh Region, with 105,000 hectares, and Tashkent Region, with 103,000 hectares. These regions can be considered major centers of wheat cultivation and important contributors to agricultural production. In contrast, regions such as Navoi, with 38,039 hectares, have relatively smaller cultivation areas, which may also correspond to lower distribution volumes.

⁴ author's development

Second, the relationship between wheat treatment density and distribution volume shows considerable regional differences. In Khorezm Region, the treatment density is particularly high, at 2.000 million units per hectare, indicating an intensive application of biological products in wheat fields. This suggests that biological protection measures in Khorezm were implemented at a high level of intensity. In contrast, treatment density is relatively low in Tashkent Region, at 0.682 million units per hectare, and Jizzakh Region, at 0.688 million units per hectare, which may indicate a comparatively lower intensity of biological product application in these areas.

Third, regional differences may be associated with wheat cultivation technologies, soil fertility, climatic conditions, pest pressure, and the organizational capacity of biolaboratories. For example, in Namangan Region, the treatment density is relatively high, at 1.507 million units per hectare, indicating intensive use of biological protection measures. However, in Jizzakh and Tashkent regions, despite their large wheat cultivation areas, the treatment density is lower, which suggests the need to further improve the planning and distribution of biological products (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Distribution density of biological product on wheat fields across regions⁵

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The analysis of the use of the Oltinko'z biological agent for pest control and preventive measures across the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2024 shows that the overall plan for its application to wheat fields was fulfilled by 101.19%. This indicates a high level of activity in the use of biological agents nationwide and reflects the intensity of agrotechnical measures. In particular, the plan was exceeded in Khorezm, Namangan, and Surkhandarya regions, which may indicate a higher level of pest risk or a greater practical need for biological protection measures in these areas.

At the same time, in Jizzakh and Tashkent regions, the plan fulfillment rate was below 70%. This may be associated with resource limitations, logistical challenges, or certain inaccuracies in regional planning. These discrepancies indicate the need to improve the balanced distribution of biological plant protection agents across the republic.

The analysis based on distribution density indicators shows important regional differences in the intensity of biological product application. In particular, in Khorezm (2.000 million units/ha), Namangan (1.507 million units/ha), and Surkhandarya (1.282 million units/ha), the density of biological products was relatively high, indicating that biological protection measures were organized more intensively in these regions. Conversely, in

⁵ author's development

Tashkent (0.682 million units/ha) and Jizzakh (0.688 million units/ha), this indicator was lower, which suggests the need to strengthen the implementation of biological control measures in these areas.

Based on the results of the study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Improve the planning system based on regional needs. Instead of applying a uniform plan for the distribution of biological products, a differentiated approach should be introduced, taking into account pest risk levels, agro-climatic conditions, and pest infestation statistics from previous years.

2. Improve the logistics and supply system. In regions where resources are limited and plans are not fully implemented, particularly in Jizzakh and Tashkent regions, it is necessary to review the logistics chain and the system for supplying biolaboratories with the required resources.

3. Standardize biological product distribution density. Normative indicators should be developed for biological product density in relation to cultivated land in each region, and a monitoring and evaluation system based on these indicators should be introduced.

4. Strengthen coordination among biolaboratories. It is advisable to improve efficiency through the exchange of experience, technological standardization, and comparison of performance indicators among regional biolaboratories.

5. Introduce a digital monitoring and management system. A digital monitoring system should be implemented to track the use of biological products, collect real-time data, and conduct timely analysis. This will improve planning accuracy, resource allocation, and the overall effectiveness of biological plant protection measures.

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